

INTEGRATIVE SIMULATION CHAIN FOR LIFETIME ASSESSMENT OF HIGHLY LOADED SHORT FIBER-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS: STATE-OF-THE-ART AND NEED FOR IMPROVEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

In this work the state of the art of the integrative simulation chain for design and dimensioning of short fibre reinforced plastics part is discussed. After introducing the single steps of this chain, the topics of weld line and damage accumulation are discussed in detail.

Considering some explicative cases, the current limitations in the prediction of weld line position are highlighted and their consequences on lifetime prediction are discussed. In particular, the influence of the mesh and the viscosity models, as available in process simulation, are analyzed, considering a plate with an insert creating a weld line. The needs for improvement in process simulation in order to enable the computation of a weld line quality variable are formulated. Concerning damage accumulation, the limitations of the commonly adopted Miner's rule are reported and the need for a basic understanding of the relevant mechanisms is stated.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of short fiber-reinforced plastic (SFRP) parts in structural applications is constantly increasing due to the advantages in terms of manufacturing costs for larger series and design freedom in shape. SFRP are mainly manufactured by injection molding process, a technology which allows for excellent reproducibility of the parts. Design and dimensioning of SFRP parts require a series of simulation steps, which are connected to each other. This chain is referred to as integrative simulation chain. The aim of this contribution is to provide an overview on the state-of-the-art regarding the integrative simulation chain for SFRPs and to point out the sources of uncertainty as well as the needs for improvement in selected steps of the chain.

2 INTEGRATIVE SIMULATION CHAIN

An integrative simulation chain for design and dimensioning of highly loaded SFRP parts manufactured by injection molding is nowadays state-of-the-art [1,2,3,4]. Refer to **Figure 1** for an example. The main steps of this chain are: injection molding process simulation, mapping of information from process simulation to structural analysis, structural analysis, and lifetime computation. Often further steps are needed, e.g. the generation of mesh on part and the manipulation of load profiles.

For each of the simulation steps, appropriate material cards have to be estimated, typically by reverse engineering procedures that require complex optimization workflows and non-standardized experimental measurements, like 3D fiber orientation measurements by computed tomography or strength evaluation (quasi-static, fatigue) on specimens with different fiber orientation distributions. Further, an optimum design requires iterations along the simulation chain to ensure the fulfillment of the application requirements, e.g. fatigue strength. For each of these tasks, specific software packages are nowadays available.

Figure 1: Example of integrative simulation chain for lifetime assessment on short fiber-reinforced thermoplastic parts.

Due to the large number of interfaces involved in the chain, both the probability of error occurrence and the effort required to transfer the information from process simulation to strength assessment are high. A standardization of such interfaces and a simplification of the simulation chain is thus more than welcome. The topic will be addressed by the European publicly funded project (ITEA3 Program) VMAP (“A new Interface Standard for Integrated Virtual Material Modelling in Manufacturing Industry”), presumably starting in September 2017.

The prediction of process-induced microstructures as local fiber orientation or weld line position is nowadays possible by injection molding simulation [5]. Currently, the most common variable considered in the simulation chain is fiber orientation. Despite some inaccuracies with respect to actual fiber orientation (e.g. in the prediction of fiber orientation at core layer in plates), the maturity degree of the chain with respect to this variable is relatively high. Other variables, instead, as weld lines and their quality, crystallinity degree, defect distributions (e.g. voids, fiber clusters), etc. are currently either only partially or not covered yet by commercial codes [6]. In the upcoming sections following topics will be discussed in more detail: weld lines and damage accumulation.

3 WELDLINES

3.1 State of the art

In the injection molding of thermoplastic parts, weld lines are formed when two melt fronts collide inside the mold cavity. Multiple injection points or complex geometries where flow is split in several melt fronts are typical causes for the formation of weld lines and are practically unavoidable in the design of engineering plastic parts. As a consequence, failure of those parts often occurs at weld lines.

Commercial injection molding simulation codes, as Autodesk Moldflow, are nowadays providing a 3D prediction of weld line position on parts. The algorithm defining the apparition of a weld line is based on the fill time result and the calculated velocity field. In Autodesk Moldflow, the meeting angle θ between two flow fronts determines the apparition of a weld line. The corresponding nodes are

classified as weld points ($0,001^\circ < \theta < 139^\circ$) or meld points ($139^\circ < \theta < 179^\circ$). The switch angle between weld and meld points is however arbitrary and lacks of clear physical meaning.

Despite the fact that most commercial codes do have an integrated mesh solver, the import of meshes generated externally by dedicated codes, e.g. Altair Hypermesh, seems to play a role on the weld line results. In **Figure 2**, the influence of mesh on the prediction of weld line position, as carried out in Moldflow 2016, is shown. Top views of two meshes are found to the left, while the respective predictions of the weld line positions are given to the right. In this example a central circular insert causes the flow separation and the formation of a weld line afterwards, as observed in

Figure 3. In the upper left picture of **Figure 2**, a symmetrical surface mesh, with progressive surface refinement at the insert (Altair Hypermesh V14.0) is presented. The last surface mesh was used to obtain a 3D solid mesh, using the solver of Autodesk Moldflow 2016. The resulting weld line (see upper right picture) is straight and covers a length of 8.5 mm. In the lower left picture, the surface mesh generated automatically by the mesh solver in Autodesk Moldflow 2016 is also presented. In this case, a mesh refinement (command *remesh area*) near to the insert was also performed. The resulting weld line (see lower right picture) is more irregular and shorter (~2.5 mm) than the one obtained with the regular mesh. In both cases, however the length of the weld line is shorter than that experimental one (see

Figure 3 on the right). Indeed, the weld line extends over the entire length of the injected plate (80 mm X 80 mm). Discrepancies in the form of the flow front, especially at the weld line and at the edges of the plate are noticeable. The weld line surface result, which indicate the end-positions of the weld line surface in 3D, is instead in better agreement with the experimental results.

Figure 2: Influence of mesh on weld line prediction: Symmetric surface mesh generated with Altair Hypermesh V14.0 (upper pictures) versus a surface mesh generated automatically by Autodesk Moldflow 2016 (lower pictures). Weld and meld points are plotted to the right.

Figure 3 Comparison of polymer melt front at 1.2 s of injection time as predicted by Autodesk Moldflow 2017.3 (on the left) and from a short-shot (on the right). The material is a PPA-GF40.

A model to predict the quality of the matrix healing at the weld line, based on the polymer reptation theory has been presented by Cruz elsewhere [7]. The model computes weld line quality as degree of matrix healing during the injection molding process. The local healing degree is estimated locally on the basis of the thermo-mechanical history of the polymer melt for a given point of the weld line. When the polymer chains at the weld line are allowed to diffuse during one reptation time, then maximal healing degree occurs, i.e. the local mechanical behavior of the matrix at the weld line and the bulk matrix material are indistinguishable. For such cases, a weld line quality value equal to 1 is assigned. On the contrary, when diffusion time is lower than one reptation time, a weld line quality value between 0 and 1 is assigned, in function of the ratio physical diffusion time to reptation time. The estimation of the weld line quality at the nodes on the part surface is challenging, because it depends strongly on the correct modeling of the heat transfer phenomena occurring at the interface polymer – mold. This would require a thermal simulation of the whole mold (metal blocks and cooling channels), in which the heat transfer coefficients between components should be carefully defined. Such surface nodes are important for fatigue strength assessment, since fatigue cracks commonly start at the surface of the part, due to geometrically-induced stress concentrations.

An additional limitation of the weld line quality computation in the algorithm proposed in [7] is that the healing estimation starts at end of filling, by supposing that healing during the filling is negligible in comparison with the rest of the injection molding cycle. However, in the case of flowing weld lines, this hypothesis is questionable. A calculation of the weld line matrix healing during filling would be possible by exporting the thermo-mechanical history of tracers placed at the weld line surface. Autodesk Moldflow allows for plotting the path of tracer particles together with the evolution of temperature, pressure and speed (Path Lines result, see Figure 4), but there is currently no option to export the temperature and pressure information of such tracer points along a given path line.

Figure 4: Path Lines result of Autodesk Moldflow on an injection molded plate with a circular central insert.

Autodesk recently launched a tool for progressive failure analysis, Helius PFA, which allows for considering the quality of weld lines into structural analysis of injection-molded plastic parts. Weld line quality computation in Helius PFA is based on a semi-empirical diffusion model, considering the flow front meeting angles, temperature and pressure histories [8]. The respective model parameters need to be calibrated on the basis of mechanical tests.

In general, the computation of weld line matrix quality can be performed by post-processing of injection molding simulation results, provided that temperature and pressure histories of each weld (and meld) end-point are stored and can be exported. In order to use the weld line quality information in the strength assessment, this data need to be mapped from the injection molding simulation mesh to the structural analysis mesh.

3.2 Need for further improvement

Referring to the state-of-the-art discussed in section 3.1, the main needs for improvement for enabling an accurate prediction of weld line matrix quality can be summarized as follow:

- Reduce the sensitivity of the weld (and meld) line result (position) with respect to the mesh density and the solver time step.
- Increase the 3D spatial resolution of the weld surface formation and weld surface movement result.
- Reduce the numerical noise associated with the weld (and meld) line result (some weld lines found by the software algorithm are numerical artefacts)
- Enable the export of the Path Lines results: temperature, pressure (and velocity) information of a tracer along a given path line, and the end-position (x,y,z) of the respective tracer.
- Introduce fiber orientation dependent viscosity models (anisotropic viscosity), which would have an influence on the velocity fields at the weld line zone and therefore on the prediction of the meeting angle between melt fronts.
- Mesh refinement (command *remesh area* in Moldflow): Include the possibility to change progressively the size of the mesh from the gross mesh to the fine mesh of a selected area.

Further, for nodes belonging to a weld line, the weld line quality information needs to be available in each step of the integrative simulation chain. Finally, proper models to correlate fatigue strength of parts with weld line quality and a methodology to properly characterize weld line fatigue strength within a relevant range of qualities as well to transfer it from specimens to parts need to be developed.

4 DAMAGE ACCUMULATION

4.1 State of the art

The simplest and most common method to compute fatigue life of plastic components under operating loadings (i.e variable amplitude load) is the Miner rule [9], which is a linear damage accumulation relationship of the type:

$$D = \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{n_i}{N_i} \right)$$

Where D is the damage, k is the number of loading steps, n_i is the applied number of cycles and N_i the number of cycles to failure of the i-th step respectively. Failure occurs when D equals the allowable damage sum D_{all} . This method can be applied under the assumption that for the i-th load step the conditions (temperature, load amplitude and load ratio) remain constant. It is available in commercial codes for lifetime prediction, as FEMFAT.

The allowable damage sum D_{all} (which should be theoretically constant and equal to 1) is usually obtained by experiments on specimens or parts under variable amplitude loads, e.g. Gassner tests.

Sonsino and Moosbrugger [10] showed that for PA66-GF35 this allowable damage sum can variate between 0.1 and 10, depending on notch radius, temperature and load ratio. Hartmann *et al.* [11] found similar values of D_{all} for a PA66-GF50 grade. Further they show that, under tension-compression loading (load ratio $R=-1$), the allowable damage sum increases with the both the size of the highly stressed volume (i.e. notch radius) and with temperature. Due to its dependency from geometry, a transfer of D_{all} from specimens to parts is highly uncertain. Further, the variability of D_{all} to load level, load ratio and temperature requires a large experimental effort to cover all relevant conditions for a given material and application. Dreißig *et al.* [13] compared the performance of 5 different damage accumulation rules on a fatigue dataset of PA66-GF35 specimens, considering the influence of fiber orientation. In all cases

allowable damage sums was affected by fiber orientation, being lower for fiber aligned in loading direction. Non-linear damage accumulation rules performed better than Miner rule. In particular, a generalized Miner rule was the best compromise between accuracy and model simplicity:

$$D = \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{n_i}{N_i} \right)^b$$

Similarly, Zago et al. [12] obtained good agreement between model prediction by generalized Miner's rule and experimental fatigue test results on short glass fiber reinforced Copolyamide coupons under different types of cyclic loads.

4.2 Need for further improvement

The investigations cited in section 4.1 clearly suggest that non-linear damage accumulation rules would be better suited for SFRPs. However, a broader campaign of investigations is necessary to get a comprehensive understanding of the behavior of SFRP under variable amplitude loadings. In particular, following influence factors on the parameters of the damage accumulation rule should be considered:

- Load level: Is there a dependency from load level? Is there a sequence effect?
- Notches: What is the effect of different stress concentrations as induced by notches? This is the key factor for transfer material characteristic values from specimens to parts.
- Load ratio: Is fatigue damage under tensile loading and compression loading different? Is a term considering creep-damage due to mean stress or blocks with constant load necessary?
- Temperature: How does damage accumulates in case the load steps occur at different temperatures? Is there a sequence effect?
- Fiber orientation
- Environment (e.g. humidity for polyamides)
- Form of the load spectrum: Are the parameter the same for other load spectra?
- Load multiaxiality: Is there a different damage under shear and tensile fatigue loading?

Based on relevant damage mechanisms occurring for the investigated materials, a suitable damage accumulation rule needs be developed and validated. Finally, the new rule has to be implemented in commercial codes for lifetime assessment.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper summarizes the state-of-the-art for the integrative simulation chain for design and dimensioning of SFRP parts under operational loads. Among potential topics for improvement, the need to consider weld lines and the need of improved damage accumulation rules have been addressed.

Concerning weld lines, both the need of enhanced viscosity models (coupling with fiber orientation) in the codes for injection molding simulation and the possibility to export additional information (e.g. path lines) is highlighted. Interfaces of the simulation chain need to be adapted to allow for the transfer of weld line quality information from the process simulation step to the lifetime assessment step.

In the case of damage accumulation, a comprehensive understanding of the damage mechanisms and their interaction, under the consideration of load level, notches, load ratio, temperature and fibre orientation is still missing. On the basis of these mechanisms, new damage accumulation rules can be developed, reducing the experimental effort for the application to further materials.

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